

EFFECTIVE METHODS OF USING COLLABORATIVE PEDAGOGY IN EDUCATION

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ANNOTATION

This article discusses effective methods for using collaborative pedagogy in the educational process. The main principles of collaborative teaching, the importance of interaction between teacher and student, the role of working in small groups in the development of learning motivation and competencies are analyzed. The use of interactive methods in the lesson process, methods aimed at developing students' independent thinking, creativity and social skills are also considered. The results of the study show that the use of collaborative pedagogy increases educational effectiveness, increases student activity and improves the level of mastery

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In today's conditions of globalization and increasing competition, the organization of education in accordance with modern requirements is one of the urgent issues. Increasing the activity of students, teaching them to think independently, communicate, and work in a team are becoming the main goals of the educational process. In this regard, cooperative pedagogy — that is, the acquisition of knowledge in cooperation between the teacher and the student, as well as between students — is one of the educational approaches that has proven its effectiveness.[1]

Cooperative pedagogy does not limit the educational process to providing knowledge alone, but is aimed at the formation of qualities such as the socio-psychological development of students, mutual respect, solidarity, and responsibility. In this approach, the teacher is not a source of knowledge, but a coordinator who organizes the learning process. Students are involved in the process not as passive listeners, but as active participants, seekers, and creators.

Modern pedagogical technologies, in particular, small group work, project-based learning, joint problem-solving, game and interactive methods, allow students to gain a deeper understanding of knowledge and develop skills for learning in a connected way. The widespread use of collaborative methods in developed educational systems around the world once again confirms the universality and effectiveness of this

approach.[2]

This article discusses the most effective methods of using collaborative pedagogy in education, their impact on student development, and recommendations for its practical application. The relevance of the study is that collaborative teaching methods play an important role in improving the quality of the educational process, democratizing the learning process, and ensuring the comprehensive development of students.

Discussion and Results

During the research, various approaches aimed at increasing the effectiveness of collaborative pedagogy in education were analyzed. The data obtained showed that the proper organization of interaction between the teacher and the student has a significant impact on student motivation. Methods such as working with small groups, exchanging ideas, and solving problems together activate students, forming in them the skills of collective responsibility and free expression of their own opinions.[3]

One of the practical aspects of collaborative pedagogy is that students do not receive knowledge from the teacher in a ready-made form, but independently acquire it in the process of research, communication, and debate. This, as a practical application of a constructive approach, enriches the educational process in content. It was observed that interactive methods used in the educational process, in particular, such as "Brainstorming", "Jigsaw", "Network Method", "Comparison Table", activate the thinking process of students.

Also, the principles of collaboration serve to increase students' interest in the lesson by creating a positive psychological environment for the educational process. Students' support for each other, and the teacher's participation as a manager and guide in the process, form a healthy environment based on mutual respect. This develops students' independence, creativity, and social competencies.[4]

One of the researchers of collaborative learning technology, R. Slavin, notes that it is not enough to simply assign students to complete tasks together. For such a process to be effective, a genuine spirit of cooperation, sincere joy at each other's successes, a willingness to provide mutual assistance, and the formation of a favorable socio-psychological environment are necessary. In this technology, the level of knowledge acquired by each student is compared not with the results of other students in the class, but with his previous indicators. Then the student, realizing that each of his small achievements is important for the team, strives to be more responsible, to search more, and to acquire knowledge consciously.[5]

In collaborative pedagogy, the student is recognized as an active subject of the educational process. In this approach, the teacher and the student become equal

participants in the pedagogical process, resulting in a collaborative learning environment. They treat each other as partners, associates, comrades, advisors, and co-managers. Collaborative relationships are formed not only between the teacher and the student, but also between the administration, parents, the community, and educators.[6] Collaborative learning technologies were created precisely on the basis of the requirements of collaborative pedagogy, and they are fundamentally different from traditional teaching. In traditional lessons, the teacher is considered the central figure - the subject of the educational process, while the student is more at the level of a passive object. Collaborative learning, on the other hand, allows for increased intrinsic motivation of the student, his or her personal thinking, independent decision-making, and active participation in the educational process. This approach, based on humanistic principles, ensures the achievement of high educational results.

The following positive results can be achieved through cooperative learning:[7]

- the student's learning process is enriched in content;
 - students absorb cognitive information that is different from each other;
 - an internal interest in the subject is formed;
 - the opportunity to strengthen personal knowledge and worldview increases;
 - the effectiveness of mutual information exchange increases;
 - the skills necessary for preparing for life are formed;
 - positive mutual understanding between different cultures and social groups develops.
- Activities based on collaborative learning technology take various forms, including:[8]
- three-step interviews,
 - roundtable discussions,
 - listing,
 - joint problem solving,
 - “one-minute” tasks,
 - paired discussions,
 - sharing problems between groups,
 - rating lines,
 - group observations,
 - active methods such as a two-part diary.

Most of these activities require dividing students into small groups and assigning them roles and tasks. The methodological, psychological, and organizational foundations of collaborative learning have been developed, which aim to focus the educational process on the individual student. This technology serves to create a creative environment, improve the quality of education, and develop students' independent thinking skills.[9]

The central processes of cooperative learning activities are the exchange of ideas, conversations, discussions, joint analysis, practical exercises, experiments and observations. The learning process is carried out in various organizational forms: “teacher-class”, “teacher-small group”, “teacher-student”, “student-student (pair work)”, “group-class”, etc. Cooperative learning provides for the activity of the teacher and students based on mutual assistance.

Main features of cooperative learning methods[10]

1. Students work together on a common task, and this group activity improves learning.
2. Groups are usually formed by 2-5 students.
3. Groups operate on the basis of socially accepted norms of cooperation.
4. Students strive to be independent and active by helping each other.
5. Each student is personally responsible for his or her own results. Non-traditional lesson forms[11]

The following types of lessons can be organized on the basis of collaborative technologies: press conference lesson, “cheerful and clever” lesson, group work lesson, peer learning lesson, student-led lesson, competition lesson, pair lesson, dialogue lesson, circular exercises lesson, and innovation lesson.

The main idea of collaborative learning is to organize joint learning in the process of joint completion of educational tasks. This method develops in students such qualities as independent thinking, creativity, a sense of self-worth, strengthening self-confidence, and a sense of responsibility. Understanding that the success of each student affects the success of the entire group, they strive to work actively on a regular basis.

Basic methods of cooperative learning[12]

1. Team learning (R. Slavin).
2. Collaborative learning in small groups (R. Slavin, 1986).
3. The “Zigzag” or “Saw” method (E. Aronson, 1978).
4. The “Let’s Read Together” method (R. Johnson, D. Johnson, 1987).
5. The method of creative research groups (Sh. Sharan, 1988).

In team learning, students are divided into two equal groups and perform the same tasks. Group members help each other, ensuring that each student makes progress in the subject. The student's results are compared with their previous performance, which encourages more active research. In the small group collaboration method, groups of 4 are formed. After explaining the topic, the teacher divides the tasks into four parts. Each student is responsible for his part, then explains it to his group, and finally a general conclusion is developed.

Factors that increase the effectiveness of cooperative learning include students' creative approach to the subject, information analysis, critical thinking, time for practical exercises, mutual assistance, etc.

In pedagogy and psychology, there are 8 forms of cooperation: introduction to the activity, independent actions together with the teacher, organization of initial actions by the teacher, imitation, auxiliary actions, self-management, self-expression, self-organization.

Collaborative learning activities aim to create a mechanism for students to work together. The result of cooperation is the emergence of new ideas, strengthening of mutual partnership, and the formation of an active position in the educational process. Joint activity initially begins with the help of the teacher and gradually turns into independent intellectual and practical actions of the student. As a result, a relationship based on partnership, cooperation, and mutual respect is formed between the teacher and the student.

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